

The Influence of the Clinical Environment on Physicians' Treatment Choices

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Variations in treatment decisions for similar patients are persistent and ubiquitous in many health care systems. Whilst patients' heterogeneous preferences and characteristics are important drivers of such variation, recent evidence suggests that provider (supply) factors are equally relevant. Focusing on the supply-side, this paper draws a distinction between physician-specific and environment-specific factors to examine whether the clinical environment in which physicians practice impacts their own treatment decisions. We focus on the choice between cemented and uncemented hip replacements, which are two common methods of fixation in this surgical procedure, with similar therapeutic success.

Methods: We employ patient-level administrative data from hip replacement surgeries performed in the English NHS between 2010 and 2016. We construct employment histories for surgeons to identify those who move from one hospital to another during the study period. This exogenous shock in the practice environment is then used to estimate the impact of the environment in their treatment decisions using a quasi difference-in-differences framework. The practice environment is defined as the rate of cemented hip replacements for all surgeons in the hospital, omitting the moving doctor's own cases.

Results: After the move, surgeons' treatment choice change on average by 0.48 percentage points for each percentage point change in the practice environment. We find that the change in a surgeon's practice style occurs right after the move with little to no further adaptation to the new environment over time. We also find no evidence of a positive sorting of surgeons to hospitals, which could be driving our results. Furthermore, we explore heterogeneous treatment effects, and find that male surgeons and surgeons with a UK medical degree are less responsive to the change in the hospital environment.

Conclusion: Our study shows that the clinical environment wherein surgeons practice significantly impacts their treatment decisions.